

A note on Pythagorean Triples

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Abstract

Some relations among Pythagorean triples are established. The main tool is a fundamental characterization of the Pythagorean triples through a chatetus which allows to determine relationships with Pythagorean triples having the same chatetus raised to an integer power.

1 Introduction

Let x , y and z be positive integers satisfying

$$x^2 + y^2 = z^2.$$

Such a triple (x, y, z) is called Pythagorean triple and if, in addition, x , y and z are co-prime, it is called primitive Pythagorean triple. First, let us recall a recent novel formula that allows to obtain all Pythagorean triples as follows.

Theorem 1.1. *(x, y, z) is a Pythagorean triple if and only if there exists $d \in C(x)$ such that*

$$x = x, \quad y = \frac{x^2}{2d} - \frac{d}{2}, \quad z = \frac{x^2}{2d} + \frac{d}{2}, \quad (1.1)$$

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with x positive integer, $x \geq 1$, and where

$$C(x) = \begin{cases} D(x), & \text{if } x \text{ is odd,} \\ D(x) \cap P(x), & \text{if } x \text{ is even,} \end{cases}$$

with

$$D(x) = \{d \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } d \leq x \text{ and } d \text{ divisor of } x^2\},$$

and if x is even with $x = 2^n k$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $k \geq 1$ odd fixed, with

$$P(x) = \{d \in \mathbb{N} \text{ such that } d = 2^s l, \text{ with } l \text{ divisor of } x^2 \text{ and } s \in \{1, 2, \dots, n-1\}\}.$$

We want to find relations between the primitive Pythagorean triple (x, y, z) generated by any predetermined x positive odd integer using (1.1) and the primitive Pythagorean triple generated by x^m with $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $m \geq 2$. In this paper we take care of relations only for the case in which the primitive triple (x, y, z) is generated with $d \in C(x)$ only with $d = 1$ and the primitive triple (x^m, y', z') is generated with $d_m \in C(x^m)$ only with $d_m = 1$ obtaining formulas that give us y' and z' directly from x, y, z . This is the first step to investigate on other relations between Pythagorean triples.

2 Results

The following theorem holds.

Theorem 2.1. *Let (x, y, z) be the primitive Pythagorean triple generated by any predetermined positive odd integer $x \geq 1$ using (1.1) with $z - y = d = 1$ and let (x^m, y', z') be the primitive Pythagorean triple generated by x^m , $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $m \geq 2$, using (1.1) with $z' - y' = d_m = 1$, we have the following formulas*

$$\begin{aligned} y' &= y \left[1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} x^{2p} \right], \\ z' &= y \left[1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} x^{2p} \right] + 1, \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

for every $m \in \mathbb{N}$ and $m \geq 2$.

Moreover we have

$$z \left[(-1)^{m-1} + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} x^{2p} \right] = \begin{cases} y' & \text{if } m \text{ is even,} \\ z' & \text{if } m \text{ is odd,} \end{cases} \quad (2.2)$$

and

$$z \left[(-1)^{m-1} + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} x^{2p} \right] + (-1)^{m-2} = \begin{cases} z' & \text{if } m \text{ is even,} \\ y' & \text{if } m \text{ is odd.} \end{cases} \quad (2.3)$$

Proof. Let x be a positive odd integer that we consider as $x = 2n + 1$, $n \in \mathbb{N}$, so that using (1.1) with $d = z - y = 1$ it gives the primitive Pythagorean triple

$$x = 2n + 1, \quad y = 2n^2 + 2n, \quad z = 2n^2 + 2n + 1, \quad (2.4)$$

while considering x^m , $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $m \geq 2$, using (1.1) with $d_m = z' - y' = 1$ it gives the primitive Pythagorean triple

$$x^m, \quad y' = \frac{x^{2m} - 1}{2}, \quad z' = \frac{x^{2m} + 1}{2}. \quad (2.5)$$

Comparing (2.4) and (2.5) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} y' &= \frac{(2n + 1)^{2m} - 1}{2} = \frac{[(2n + 1)^2 - 1]}{2} [(2n + 1)^{2(m-1)} + (2n + 1)^{2(m-2)} + \dots + 1] \\ &= \frac{(4n^2 + 4n)}{2} \left[1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (2n + 1)^{2p} \right] = (2n^2 + 2n) \left[1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (2n + 1)^{2p} \right] = y \left[1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} x^{2p} \right], \end{aligned}$$

which is the first part of (2.1), and because $d_m = z' - y' = 1$ we also obtain

$$z' = y \left[1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} x^{2p} \right] + 1,$$

which is the second of (2.1).

Moreover, if m is odd, using (2.4) and (2.5) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} z' &= \frac{(2n + 1)^{2m} + 1}{2} = \frac{[(2n + 1)^2 + 1]}{2} [(2n + 1)^{2(m-1)} - (2n + 1)^{2(m-2)} + \dots - (2n + 1)^2 + 1] \\ &= (2n^2 + 2n + 1) \left[1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} (2n + 1)^{2p} \right] = z \left[1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} x^{2p} \right], \end{aligned}$$

which is the second case of (2.2), and because $d_m = z' - y' = 1$ we obtain also

$$y' = z \left[1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} x^{2p} \right] - 1,$$

which is the second case of (2.3).

Finally, if m is even, we prove that

$$y' = z \left[-1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} x^{2p} \right], \tag{2.6}$$

which is the first case of (2.2) and because $d_m = z' - y' = 1$ we also obtain

$$z' = z \left[-1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1-p} (-1)^{m-1-p} x^{2p} \right] + 1,$$

which is the first case of (2.3).

To do that we use (2.4) and (2.5) to write

$$\frac{(2n + 1)^{2m} - 1}{2} = (2n^2 + 2n + 1) \left[-1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} (2n + 1)^{2p} \right], \tag{2.7}$$

and we prove that (2.7) is an identity. In fact

$$\begin{aligned} (2n + 1)^{2m} - 1 &= (4n^2 + 4n + 2) \left[-1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} (2n + 1)^{2p} \right], \\ (2n + 1)^{2m} - 1 &= [(2n + 1)^2 + 1] \left[-1 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} (2n + 1)^{2p} \right], \\ (2n+1)^{2m} &= -(2n+1)^2 + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} (2n+1)^{2(p+1)} + \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} (-1)^{m-1-p} (2n+1)^{2p}, \\ (2n + 1)^{2m} &= -(2n + 1)^2 + \left[(-1)^{m-2} (2n + 1)^4 + (-1)^{m-3} (2n + 1)^6 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (-1)^{m-4} (2n + 1)^8 + \dots - (2n + 1)^{2(m-1)} + (2n + 1)^{2m} \right] \\ &\quad + \left[(-1)^{m-2} (2n + 1)^2 + (-1)^{m-3} (2n + 1)^4 + (-1)^{m-4} (2n + 1)^6 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (-1)^{m-5} (2n + 1)^8 + \dots - (2n + 1)^{2(m-2)} + (2n + 1)^{2(m-1)} \right], \tag{2.8} \end{aligned}$$

and, because m is even, after simplifying (2.8) we get

$$(2n - 1)^{2m} = (2n - 1)^{2m},$$

so we proved that (2.7) is an identity. Therefore, (2.6) holds. Consequently, formulas (2.1), (2.2) and (2.3) have thus been proved.

Obviously, because $z - y = d = 1$, we can also obtain other relations between (x, y, z) and (x^m, y', z') ; for example, (2.1) is equivalent to

$$y' = z + y \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} x^{2p} - 1,$$

$$z' = z + y \sum_{p=1}^{m-1} x^{2p}.$$

Similarly, we can obtain other relations from (2.2) and (2.3). □

We illustrate formulas (2.1), (2.2) and (2.3) by the following example.

Example 2.1. We give the following table that can be extended for each primitive triples x, y, z , and x^s, y', z' with $x - y = 1$ and $x' - y' = 1$.

Using (2.1) we obtain

$x = 3$	$y = 4$	$z = 5$
$x = 3^2$	$y' = 4(1 + 3^2) = 40$	$z' = 41$
$x = 3^3$	$y' = 4(1 + 3^2 + 3^4) = 364$	$z' = 365$
$x = 3^4$	$y' = 4(1 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 3^6) = 3280$	$z' = 3281$
$x = 3^5$	$y' = 4(1 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 3^6 + 3^8) = 29524$	$z' = 29525$
$x = 3^6$	$y' = 4(1 + 3^2 + 3^4 + 3^6 + 3^8 + 3^{10}) = 265720$	$z' = 265721$
$\vdots$	$\vdots$	$\vdots$

While using (2.2) and (2.3) we obtain

$x = 3$	$y = 4$	$z = 5$
$x = 3^2$	$y' = 5(-1 + 3^2) = 40$	$z' = 41$
$x = 3^3$	$z' = 5(1 - 3^2 + 3^4) = 365$	$y' = 364$
$x = 3^4$	$y' = 5(-1 + 3^2 - 3^4 + 3^6) = 3280$	$z' = 3281$
$x = 3^5$	$z' = 5(1 - 3^2 + 3^4 - 3^6 + 3^8) = 29525$	$y' = 29524$
$x = 3^6$	$y' = 5(-1 + 3^2 - 3^4 + 3^6 - 3^8 + 3^{10}) = 265720$	$z' = 265721$
$\vdots$	$\vdots$	$\vdots$

References

- [1] R. Amato, *A characterization of pythagorean triples*, JP Journal of Algebra, Number Theory and Applications, **39**, (2017), 221–230
- [2] W. Sierpinski, *Elementary theory of numbers*, PWN-Polish Scientific Publishers, 1988.